

TERMS OF USING VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL MEANS IN COMMUNICATION**Nizomiddin Qo'ldashev Axmadaliyevich****f.f.d.(PhD) Farg'ona davlat universiteti****Filologiya kafedrası o`qituvchisi****O`rmonova Mohirabonu Muhammadali qizi****Farg'ona davlat universiteti****Magistratura bo`limi Lingvistika (ingliz tili) magistranti****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7891407>**

Abstract. Non-verbal in the process of communication the use of tools instead of verbal tools, their use in speech the need to emerge, the human body parts of the speaker's thoughts, the voice through tone, clothing, and coded symbols expression, their role in communication, tasks and speech to carry out scientific-research works on the provision of savings special importance is observed in this article.

Key words. Gender language, body language, non-verbal, verbal, communication, paralinguistic influence, customs, tone.

In nearly all situations, verbal and non-verbal tools are combined in some sense the function of conditional symbols when used parallel passes. When used from a linguistic point of view, usually the verb and its different gestures and actions are used to convey their meaning. In this, a person communicates with his non-verbal actions experience or relationship to the listener (longing, joy, gratitude, caress, shame, cut, regret, upset, can express displeasure, moods, etc. In turn, non-verbal means when expressing the name of an object, its quality occupation of meaning through character aspects (fat, thin, tall, small, etc.) is enough. It should be said that not only in ancient times, but also even now, greetings in high circles have been raised to the level of art. Complex, repetitive, and time-consuming movements associated with gait the manner of greeting expressed deep respect and loyalty. With the passage of time, the worldview of each nation, in relation to the environment of greeting based on the norms of attitude and cultural demand different forms are accepted. In many nations of the world, it is including in English, greeting processes are mainly verbal communication although it is done through hands, head and body in other nations Actions with the help of other organs create additional respect for people, love between people, and from a psychological point of view, the resentment between and removes enmity. From a linguistic point of view, it is in communication increases the effectiveness of verbal means.

In general, verbal means are national in the process of communication associated with customs, values, certain individuals, groups and regions aspects have not yet been fully explored. Especially theirs non-verbal the issue of parallel use with tools has not been thoroughly studied. This approach to the problem is a spiritual and psychological portrait of the human personality to clarify, his behavior, interests in every way to learn, speech activity with the physiological structure of a person that they always move in close connection with each other. It is natural that it helps to clarify. Because of linguistics the main task is to learn all the intricacies of the human language. He looked at the surface even the smallest seemingly insignificant element is the end as a result, it is the most important element that controls the movement of the whole head system can be.

In modern linguistic, the field of paralinguistics assessment of non-verbal means interpreted by researchers from the descriptive stage to semiotic, linguistic and cultural studies and was

taken to the linguistic and psychological stage. A lot of theoretical feedback was given about the tools, data combined, grouped and according to the purpose of application that it is possible to demonstrate one's superiority through verbal means expressed. In a word, non-verbal and verbal communication interdependence and independence of one another as a means of demonstrating its superiority found scientific and practical proof. Traditions, values and communication characteristic of the Uzbek nation along with the fact that culture is becoming more and more popular in the country to develop their own languages to the different nationalities that have been living there, all opportunities to preserve national and created religious values.

Fortunately, Uzbek by other nationalities and peoples to respect national holidays, values and traditions, national and local character in the process of their implementation as well as mastering non-verbal means among verbal means cases of appropriate use in their speeches are also emerging should be evaluated as a positive case. But the Uzbek language is so subtle. There are non-verbal means that are used to understand communication time and coverage will not be sufficient. Accordingly, national culture, non-verbal means that embody customs and manners interest in learning is growing. These interests within the framework of linguistic and cultural studies, it should be noted that it is progressing. Non-verbal means of national culture, traditions and values is the most convenient means of preservation. It is a very delicate communication that cannot be described by simple words to the future generations supply forms serve to give. In addition, music, theater, sculpture, understanding of art forms such as painting, poetry, painting, their non-verbal means are an important link in understanding the secrets that are passing. Therefore, non-verbal tools are used by linguists, sociologists, psychologists, cultural scientists, philosophers, historians, art critics, became the object of research of literary experts and representatives of other fields.

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